

Medical Diagnosis Awareness

Brief Understanding of Neuro-Medication Effects and How it Effects our Physical Body

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Abstract:- Medical diagnosis awareness, General idea on what are the critical health issues relating to physics of body and its existence rather than it's chemical nature through a short story.

Keywords:- Boundary Layer Theory, Smoking Weed, Neuro Medicine, Corona Virus.

I. KEY PROCEDURE IN BOUNDARY LAYER THEORY AND HOW I LEARNED IT

Firstly, lets understand the physics of living, during my graduation 3rd year in 2020, it was the starting of corona virus, and I was given weed in 2nd year July month that's in 2019, It's my first start, ever since I continued till November 2020. I used to be thin and smoking weed gives a very good feeling and I was highly smoked weed for one week and 3rd year 1st semester is near and there was a subject where lecture on boundary layer theory is currently going on and I got notes in the form of pdf via WhatsApp, prepared by IIT staff and I opened it and start reading then I saw a formula which is

$$P\text{-applied} = P\text{-atmospheric pressure}$$

Suddenly I thought about how bong bottle works which I am smoking and I have taken pen and book and started drawing the side view of bong bottle to understand the physics behind it, I thought I have to apply certain pressure at the opening nozzle of bong bottle, at top and it has a stencil which acts a throttle with change in area decreases and the velocity of flow increases and is inserted at an angle to the bottom of the bong bottle and we need to suck it, same procedure with cigarette where we need to apply certain pressure, in general everything stays at atmospheric pressure we adapt to that pressure to live like from plants to living organisms lives at different pressure zones. We humans are born from mother's womb at certain pressure that equals the mothers body pressure but suddenly at nine months we come out start adapting to live with the nature and atmosphere around us at atmospheric pressure that's why people call it's a birthday and maintain individual body pressure adapting to heat and cold and other climates and learns to survive on our own.

Now coming back to smoking weed, initially the bong bottle at down nozzle with stash (bunch of crushed weed leaves) inserted and upper opening nozzle are equalized by

atmospheric pressure at both ends, we need to apply pressure that's more than atmospheric pressure in order to make the stash burn to smoke to come out of opening nozzle connecting the throat. And the formula changes to

$$P\text{-suction pressure (P-applied)} > P\text{-atmospheric pressure}$$

I used to go for bigger stash to be burned so that I applied pressure that's more than atmospheric pressure squeezing my brain nerves and after releasing the smoke to get out of stomach makes the after effects of weed and it feels good. The stash does vibrate the body and those waves open the pores of the body which is healthy, makes us feel really nice.

Actually what happens with boundary layer theory is, if we consider airplane wing, its tilted to some angle from up to low that's what responsible for the lift but when air passing near the wing due to motion of wing passing through the air is responsible to lift the plane via it's wing and at some distance from up to lower tilt, suction pressure is applied because after hitting the wing due to its tilt the air must pass through the wing and heats up going further and increases the velocity with lower viscosity that means the air tries to move away from the wing causing uneven distribution of air at the wing and sucking that hot air decreases the uneven distribution of air at the wing causing smoother airflow at the wing leads to stable balance which reduces the noise and vibrations at the wing further reducing whole plane body vibrations resulting to smooth lift.

II. AFTER EFFECTS OF NEURO MEDICINE AND PERSONAL EXPERIENCE OF USING IT

I had completed 2nd year 2nd semester exams and little bit of disturbed at the end of the year with all smoking weed thing also I cannot stop controlling smoking weed and cigarettes and one day I acted different my energy levels had gone down and I had inner voices and rehearses of situations that happened before in my head and I can't breathe and I talked something rubbish with my father, he immediately took me to a neuro hospital and I came out of the hospital I am feared that I remembered that doctor told me that I cannot smoke weed anymore because after medication if I smoke he told me that I may die, I felt itself in the hospital and left it, next day morning my father and his brothers feared of me and booked a car and taken me to hospital for medication and I

was given an injection to sleep and he given me tablets I did taken them and I stayed in the hospital for one week and diagnosed with medicine like all I ate is food with medicine and sleep, kept leave in college for one month and stayed at home because my father refused to send me to college that if I may smoke weed again, after one month I again gone to college for 3rd year 2nd semester is going on, I cannot control myself to stop smoking weed so I again smoked it at the terrace I almost feel like my heart beat raised and my whole body vibrating rapidly that I am shaking and thought dying laying in my bed had a brain stroke, it really shaken the shit out of me that I promised myself not to smoke again, at the end of the semester my attendance is very low, very close to detention so I went home packing bags then after news came like corona virus came to our state in India and given holidays, I continued the medication for almost two years because doctor recommended it.

Suddenly days passing by, my health is not good and white color powder is coming out of forehead. At first, I thought it was dandruff like I never had dandruff before medication on my head. I told doctor about it, he said that it was nothing and I ignored it. I started feeling senselessness on my forehead and after some days, one day I got fever and my ears blocked, unable to breathe, I tried with some ear drops at local market the drops are not reaching my eardrum I can't sense it like I lost sense the eardrops not reaching down and I was like what happened until I did a research on internet that using neuro medicine for almost a year may cause severe health issue especially when not medicated properly the situation cannot be treated further.

Power is defined as work done per unit time, i.e.,

$$\text{Power (P)} = \text{Ability to Work (W)} / \text{Time (T)}$$

As time goes by power decreases that's why there is an expire date for everything, it won't do work anymore when expired.

Plants, humans, bacteria grow by natural law which by means of breathing and after expired acts as manure but medicine on the other hand poisons the food when expired.

Its like the medicines they got power, not life. They are used to treat mild symptoms and usually doctors recommend 3 days, one week or one month, but this doctor played with my balls and I believed him until some white powder coming out of my ears when I cleaned with ear buds after treating with ear drops, they pain so much that ear bud is not travelling in to the ear, I don't know what's stopping it.

Eating organic food makes us healthy and become parts of our body, while tablets or medicines on the other hand which are costly and been made in a factory unlike food, not made from food materials, based on some chemical reactions and without understanding the physics and after effects, they are designed and manufactured to cure diseases like curing mental diseases that weren't present or high dosage may cause the tablets to stay in the body for a long time causing sinus problems including face vibrations, shaking, closing of

nose and ear pores so that may leads to heating of the blood cells to a point that the whole body raises its temperature and may choke the life out of us.

Plants, they find a way to grow in the environment and come out of soil controlling and adapting the choke of life, that's breathing. On the other hand English medicine not organic life based nor physical based but chemical reaction based used to treat diseases and may work for some time but lose their power after sometime and overmedication may lead to staying of the medicine in our body and become useless and that powder after losing its power and it's high content stays in the brain if it neuro medicine and I mean that's a lot of waste closing the pores of our body also nerves and blood vessels resulting to irregular blood flow to the heart, same issue with drugs, unlike weed or tobacco they cannot be grown in the soil or water.

Heavy raising of body temperature may lead to harden the powder particles at one place and they block certain parts like brain, nose and ears if its neuro medicines and we need to go for a surgery to remove waste out of our body which costs further and sometimes may lead to death

One of my elders in the village told me to try to eat tamarind more where it has the power to cleanse nostrils and regulate blood flow and increases the sense of brain. I have tried it, now I got like more glue coming out of my ears along with white powder and I was like why do doctors play for money. Even if I complaint they would ignore me for smoking weed. It was because of my father's lack of intelligence and understanding the home problems. Considering that I was a puppet of doctor is still getting my nerves, moving on with consciousness is necessary in life. We can't control the injustice happened to us but moving out of it and lead a peaceful life that no one gives free.

Also after effects of neuro medicine:

- *gaining over weight*
- *lose thinking ability*
- *may lose sensual content in the body resulting to hardening of cells causing tumors*
- *body will prone to narcotics*
- *Making the body numb*

Getting back from neuro medication to live a normal life, at first, it feels like whenever got sick we need to see a doctor but try to normalize thinking by getting body pressure and blood pressures to normal and do not overthink and controlling it by frequent exercises doing some hard work and getting healthy food so no need to take those medicines again. To overcome this, one need to get aware of this medicine to not to use for overtime like a year even if the doctor prescribes. Afterall its psychology not true health.

III. HOW CORONA VIRUS ORIGINATED IN THE WORLD AND LATEST ADVANCED TECHNOLOGY IN PICTURE

From the fact that it's the first human infected disease in the mankind history (not passed from any animal or passed to an animal in its history), there are three main possible causes of it. they are,

- A. Apart from symptoms when we look at physical biology of the blood platelets have many innerparts inside it as I learned from school, from biology but what happened to blood platelets is, it's not some separate virus that's born, its our blood platelets starts infecting one another because it's a sinus disease, that passes from person to other person quickly through inhaling and exhaling process polluting the atmosphere around us and causes the pores of the blood cells to close and make them heat up the blood flow causing tentacles coming out of blood cells becoming ball like structures with fins coming out as we observe corona virus there are some tentacles outside the red ball like structure used to cool faster the cells fluids got evaporated and further resulting to squeezing of cells and not able to come out and therefore unable to move and starts infecting other cells around it. they search for fluids and passes the disease to next cell by sucking the energy out of it yet its time will be over and be active for certain period of time, they are so small that they even evaporates through the air in the mouth or nose and come out of body but everything loses power with respect to time and become expires.
- B. Since the viruses are smaller than blood cells containing their own genetic code they used to kill the cells but if that's the case their count is to increase like they lay down eggs inside like a paddy tree is giving seeds. And live in poor conditions.
- C. Viruses are made out of semen ('cum'), vaginal fluids or infected blood enters the body due to their poor living conditons they create an environment around it that squeezed cells become viruses keep on attaching to clean cells and pass that disease as going on. 'viruses are nothing but diseased cells containing cell's genetic code'.

Corona virus after 2022 world tufan, started in rainy season wiped the whole countries like india, dubai, southern countries with floods, the cases have drastically decreased and corona virus almost disappeared in the world.

It might seems superstitious but people inventing different technologies with same basic principles and formulas and, same with corona virus, it was not grow in rainy season and during rainy season in india most cases dissappeared than winter and summer seasons, passes without contact extended like the most advanced version that terrorred the world I don't know how the disease passed across the world because it's a sinus related disease that may trap heat inside the body by trapping heat inside it has many degrees of freedom and the fact that chinese experimented with sperm cells to find out genetic code long before they are biologically more advanced than creating machines that they even have ancient treatment came to china from india which is physical in nature that are today replaced with english chain mechanisms (chemical in nature) and even calling humans as most sophisticated chemical factory on the other hand before chemistry came to india we all believed in physical nature and people understand it differently that the way peroidic table influenced the world to believe that our view shifted to chemical nature and on the other hand physical nature is defines as "the exixtence of a body with complex mechanisms to grow and decay", the way bodhi dharma cured chinese diseases at that time going all the way from india to china, even chinese build temples for him, even chinese build temples for the creator, no where found in the whole universe, we build temples for fighters.

"Buddhism mainly focuses on curing diseases through physical embodiment"

The chain mechanisms are invented long before 20th century and from the west the technology and age of computers came and drastically changed the world in the 20th century to think about smartness relating to controlling of mechanisms that can create robots and may be evolved to build themselves in the future and seeing how far we came with the AI, once believed as robots talking to each other in movies, Now made of steel and diodes and current now the idea changed from being a chemical factory to physical existence (matter, echo motion and visualization)

I think the next technology that's being developed is based on choke pressure adding to AI, we call it Dassault being that adapt to staying stable at different places and zones of terror.

Even modern rockets use choke pressure principle to be stable while landing, like how our human brain senses and controls the blood pressure and maintain to live at it.

Most advanced technology that humans seeing now is Dassault fighter jets and rockets, even making more vulnerable to adapt in different zones travelling longer distances.

The fact that corona virus almost become a singularity that out of 700 million people infected by corona virus, almost 7 million people died across the world lead to a global pandemic that even became a singularity of life at that time, that became the cause to unable to predict the next global pandemic because corona virus still remains a mystery.

IV. CONCLUSION

The technological singularity is a hypothetical future event in which artificial intelligence (AI) will have surpassed human intelligence, leading to a rapid and exponential increase in technological development.

Not only in technology but in life the singularity plays an orthogonal role in which the next living species or viruses may surpass the human race together decreasing the life expectancy, goodly, singularity only exists in predictions related to evolution of species to next generation, as we humans too through technology.

REFERENCES

- [1]. Boundary-Layer Theory, Herrmann Schlichting, Springer Science & Business Media, 20-May-2003 - Technology & Engineering - 800 pages.
- [2]. The Singularity is Near: *When Humans Transcend Biology*, Ray Kurzweil, Viking, September-2005 – 652 pages.